

Conductometric and Thermochemical Studies in Non-Aqueous Solvents. Part II. Nature of Solutions of Protonic Acids in *n*-Butanol

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Nature of the solutions of fluorosulphuric, disulphuric, sulphuric, trichloroacetic and dichloroacetic acids in *n*-butanol has been studied using conductometric and thermochemical techniques. The following order of the strength of acids has been observed:

Neutralisation reactions of these acids with organic tertiary bases have also been studied in butanol and comparison of heats of neutralisation in various alcohols has been made.

Titration of fluorosulphuric and disulphuric acids against these bases have also been carried out using visual indicators. It has been suggested that *n*-butanol undergoes autoprotolysis as :

A study of the saturation solubility of hydrogen chloride in different alcohols has been taken as basis for comparing the basic strength of these alcohols and it has been reported that their basic strength increases with increase in chain length¹. However, sufficient data supporting this generalisation is not available. Physico-chemical studies in methanol and ethanol have already been reported from these laboratories⁷. In this communication an attempt has been made to investigate the nature of the solutions of protonic acids in *n*-butanol with help of conductometric and thermochemical studies.

EXPERIMENTAL

n-Butanol (BDH AnalaR) was further purified as reported². Fluorosulphuric, disulphuric, sulphuric, trichloroacetic and dichloroacetic acids were prepared and/or purified as reported earlier³. The bases other than quinoline were stored over potassium hydroxide beads and distilled. Following fractions were collected for use :

(a) α -picoline 127–28°/735 mm. (b) pyridine 112–13°/737 mm. (c) dimethyl aniline 192–93°/741 mm. Quinoline was purified through the formation of zinc chloride complex and the fraction distilling at 228–29°/740 mm. was collected for use.

Calorimeter : An isothermal phase change calorimeter designed after Dainton *et al.*⁴ was employed for thermochemical measurements. Diphenyl ether was used as the dilatometric

1. W. Gerrard and E. D. Macklen, *J. Appl. Chem (London)*, 1959, **9**, 85.
2. A. Weissberger and E. S. Proskauer, 'Organic Solvents', Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York (1955), 346.
3. R. C. Paul and K. C. Malhotra, *Res. Bull. Pb. Univ. Chandigarh*, 1965, **16**, 251.
4. F. S. Dainton, K. J. Diaper, K. J. Ivin, and D. R. Shear, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 1269.

fluid and thus all determinations were carried out at its melting point (26.9°). The experimental error changed a little with weight of the solute but in no case was more than 1%.

Heat of Solution : Freshly distilled solvent (25 ml.) was transferred to the dry reaction vessel from which all traces of moisture had been expelled by passing a current of dry nitrogen for 10–15 minutes. A known amount of the solute (taken in a fragile glass bulb) was transferred into it. Thermostats were operated till the contents of the vessel attained their temperature which was indicated by the uniform drift rate. It was invariably zero. The dissolution of the solute was then initiated by breaking the glass bulb with sharp end of the stirrer. Five to six experiments were carried out with varying amounts of acids.

Heat of neutralisation : For the heat of neutralisation 100 ml of the acid solution was prepared in cold and 25 ml. of this solution was transferred to the reaction vessel. A known amount of the base solution (sealed in a glass bulb) was transferred into it. After the equilibrium was attained, the glass bulb was broken and the enthalpy values were calculated as amount of heat evolved per mole of the base neutralised.

For the measurement of equivalent conductance, solvent was taken in a dry measuring flask and a known amount of the acid was added to the ice cooled solvent and the volume made upto 25 ml. The acid solution (5 ml.) was transferred to the dip type conductivity cell, placed in an oil bath maintained at $25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The conductivity bridge (Toshniwal type CL 01/01) was used for measuring conductance of the solution. For conductometric titrations, a three necked vessel flushed with dry nitrogen and fitted with electrodes, a micro-burette and silica gel drying tube, was used. The acid solution was added to the base solution taken in the titration flask. Change in conductance was measured after each addition.

Transference of materials, as far as possible, was carried out in dry box.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Equivalent conductance of fluorosulphuric, disulphuric, sulphuric, trichloroacetic and dichloroacetic acids has been measured in *n*-butanol in the concentration range $3.5\text{--}48.5 \times 10^{-5}$ mole/litre. The plots of λ_c versus \sqrt{C} show a linear relationship (Fig. 1). Equivalent conductance at infinite dilution (λ_0) has been obtained by extrapolation to zero concentration and the values are recorded below :

Acid	λ_0
Fluorosulphuric acid	32.70
Disulphuric acid	23.33
Sulphuric acid	12.40
Trichloroacetic acid	3.33
Dichloroacetic acid	1.66

n-Butanol has a dielectric constant 17.1 at 25° and thus the ionisation of these acids is expected to be low as compared to their solutions in water. The solutions of these acids

5. A. Wiessberger and E. S. Proskauer, 'Organic Solvents', Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York (1955), 94.

were prepared in cold and are quite stable at room temperature for a sufficient length of time (30 hr) as is indicated by the consistent values of their molar conductance.

FIG 1 EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE OF PROTONIC ACIDS
IN BUTANOL AT 25°

Heats of solution of these acids in *n*-butanol have been measured and recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Heats of solution of various protonic acids in butanol (25 ml)

Acid	Amount of acid g.mole $\times 10^5$	Heat of solution $-\Delta H$ kcal/mole
HSO ₃ F	25.6	24.9
	51.0	24.9
	99.6	24.9
	152.0	25.3
	153.0	25.3
H ₂ S ₂ O ₇	23.7	50.1
	35.9	46.1
	45.0	42.9
	78.4	42.6
	84.8	41.9
H ₂ SO ₄	52.0	15.5
	92.9	12.6
	109.0	12.5
	123.5	12.4
	238.9	11.2
CCl ₃ COOH	22.8	2.7
	45.9	2.7
	50.0	2.5
	60.9	2.5
	76.3	2.5
CHCl ₂ COOH	73.0	1.7
	87.7	1.7
	115.0	1.8
	177.5	1.6

Heat of solution of a protonic acid is the net result of the heat of solvate formation between acid and the solvent, heat of ionisation of the solvate and heat of solvation of the ions produced. It has been observed that heat of solution of dibasic acids is concentration dependent. This may be explained to be due to incomplete ionisation of the second proton.

n-Butanol is a basic solvent with respect to these acids and thus may be protonated. Conductance and thermochemical behaviour of these acids may, therefore, be explained by the following equations :

For monobasic acids

For dibasic acids

On the basis of λ_0 values and average heat of solution in *n*-butanol, the acids may be arranged in the following order of decreasing strength :

Organic tertiary bases are freely miscible with *n*-butanol giving slightly conducting solutions. Heats of solution of these bases in butanol has also been found to be quite low (0.78–1.87 K.Cal per mole)⁶. These bases are strong proton acceptors and may accept proton from butanol. The reaction may be represented by the following equation :

A comparison of the conductance and heats of solution of protonic acids and organic tertiary bases clearly indicate that the solvent is predominantly basic in nature. In order to further understand the ionisation of the solvent and the nature of the solutions of protonic acids and bases in it, neutralisation reactions between the protonic acids and the tertiary organic bases have been studied conductometrically, thermochemically as well as by using visual indicator dyes in this medium.

Conductometric titrations have been carried out between fluorosulphuric, disulphuric and sulphuric acids and α -picoline (Fig. 2). The breaks in the curves indicate that fluorosulphuric acid and disulphuric acid form normal salts whereas sulphuric acid forms only the acid salt. As is evident from the λ_0 values, sulphuric acid is a weaker acid and is not sufficiently ionised at this concentration to give normal salts.

6. R. C. Paul, K. S. Dhindsa, S. C. Ahluwalia and S. P. Narula, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 641.

7. R. C. Paul, H. M. Kapil, S. S. Pahl and S. C. Ahluwalia, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 720.

Titrations of the protonic acids with quinoline, α -picoline, pyridine and dimethyl aniline have been carried out using methyl red, methyl orange and dimethyl yellow as indicators. The end points have been detected by the change in colour from yellow in the basic to crimson red, orange red and blood-red respectively in slightly acidic solutions. The maximum deviation of the experimental and the theoretical end point is 1.5%.

FIG 2 CONDUCTANCE TITRATIONS OF α -PICOLINE VERSUS PROTONIC ACIDS IN BUTANOL AT 25°C

Heats of neutralisation of tertiary organic bases with protonic acids have been measured and presented in Table III. The enthalpy change accompanying the neutralisation reactions varies between 6.5–8.5 K.Cal per mole. Since the acids have been taken in excess, even the dibasic acids are likely to act as monobasic acids. The neutralisation reactions may be explained by the following equations :

TABLE III

Heats of neutralisation of protonic acids with various bases in butanol (25 ml)

Acid	Base	Heat of reaction - ΔH kcal/mole*
HSO_3F	α -Picoline	8.4
	Pyridine	8.1
	Dimethyl aniline	6.7
$\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$	α -Picoline	7.5
	Pyridine	7.4
H_2SO_4	α -Picoline	8.4
	Pyridine	8.4
	Dimethyl aniline	7.6
CCl_3COOH	α -Picoline	5.6
	Pyridine	4.5
	Dimethyl aniline	4.7

* The values given are the mean values of 4–5 experiments for the acid-base neutralisation.

Neutralisation reactions :

where B is a base.

No solid separated out during the course of these reactions. Since the acids and the bases have been taken in butanol, the enthalpy change is due to the reaction 3. The salts (BH^+A^-) are soluble in butanol, and the solutions are conducting. Due to the low dielectric constant of butanol, the salt, however, may not be completely ionised and may exist as ion pairs in equilibrium with the ions. It may be suggested, therefore, that the major enthalpy change in these reactions is due to the formation of butanol from its ions and the heat change due to the formation of salt makes relatively small contribution.

The neutralisation enthalpies in the case of trichloroacetic acid are comparatively low. Since acid is incompletely dissociated, heat may be absorbed to ionise the solvate formed as a result of the progress of neutralisation reaction.

Heat of neutralisation from its ions in the case of butanol compares well with those of ethanol and methanol⁷, suggesting that it may also undergo autoprotolysis as

However, no significant effect of the change of basicity of alcohol due to change of alkyl group has been observed in heat of neutralisation.

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Received January 15, 1971